

PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS OF FIBRE PREFORMS BASED ON FLOW FRONT AND PRESSURE MEASUREMENT

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SUMMARY: This contribution deals with the experimental characterisation of a textile fabric in a single experiment. For this reason a mathematical model has been build up that allows to calculate pressure distribution and the flow front position during the injection for permeability measurement. This model was implemented in a software that controls and evaluates the measurement. Although every kind of sensor that detects the flow front could be used within this software, pressure sensors were chosen due to their continuous information about the injection. In contrast to sensors that detect the flow front, pressure sensors give further information about the injection even after the flow front has passed them. The designed cell is equipped with a glass lid that makes simultaneous visual tracking of the injection possible. First measurements showed stable result values, particularly the direction of the principal axes can be detected clearly.

KEYWORDS: Permeability measurement, online evaluation, ultrasonic sensor, pressure sensor.

INTRODUCTION

For optimal part quality in Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), process simulations help finding optimum process parameters, thus reducing development and manufacturing time and costs. Darcy's law is currently used to describe flow in fibre preforms. It states the flow velocity to be proportional to the fluids viscosity and the pressure gradient in the medium:

$$\vec{v} = -\frac{[K]}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \vec{\nabla} p \quad (1)$$

\vec{v} : flow velocity
 η : fluid viscosity
 $[K]$: permeability tensor
 Φ : porosity
 $\vec{\nabla} p$: pressure gradient

Up to now there is no reliable model to predict the permeability tensor K because of the complexity of the geometrical configuration of the fibre structures [1]. In this paper an experimental setup is presented that allows to determine the permeability tensor in a single experiment. Because of the high scatter of permeability it is necessary to conduct several measurements to obtain reliable data. Thus for parametric studies – i.e. like examination of the influence of the shear angle on the permeability tensor – many experiments are required.

The focus in the development of this tool was therefore to minimize the effort to setup the experiment and particularly to reduce the effort to evaluate the permeability.

In the two-dimensional (2D) case, the radial propagation of the liquid into the porous preform is elliptic (fig. 1). The maximum and minimum radial extents R_1 and R_2 and the orientation φ characterise the elliptical flow front position:

Fig. 1: Radial propagation of the liquid into the fibre structure with the principal permeabilities K_1 and K_2 and the orientation φ .

In order to achieve reliable permeability data, a large extend of the flow front ellipse is required. The cell has a cavity of 400 x 400 mm, with an adaptable cavity height. It includes pressure sensors and up to 8 ultrasonic (US) sensors. For flow-front monitoring, the ultrasonic principles “Interface Change” [2] is used. In contrast to US-sensors, the signals of pressure transducers can be evaluated even after the flow-front has passed the Sensor.

Data processing in the 2D-measurements is based on the same principle as in the 3D-case. Yet, the relation between permeability and the flow front position differs. In 3D case the pressure drops faster with increasing distance from the injection gate than in 2D case, since the 3D-flow front is semi-ellipsoidal whereas the 2D-flow front is elliptical.

FLOW MODEL

To calculate the permeability within a preform based on measured pressure data and flow front positions, a mathematical model of the injection is required. Particularly for sensors that detect the flow front like ultrasonic sensors a flow model is required that involves the time history. This is because that kind of sensors generally does not display the flow front position at a time but discrete positions at discrete times.

A basic assumption is that the permeability is homogeneous within the test cell. This means that the flow in the measurement cell can be assumed to be pure radial, independent of the orthotropic properties of the permeability. For incompressible fluids the equation of continuity is formulated as

$$\vec{\nabla} v = 0 \quad (2)$$

Combining this equation with Darcy’s Law (Eqn. 1) leads to the Laplace equation which describes the pressure distribution within the fluid. The Laplace equation can be expressed in polar coordinates as

$$2D: \quad \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{dp}{dr} + \frac{d^2 p}{dr^2} = 0 \quad \begin{array}{l} p : \text{pressure} \\ r : \text{radius} \end{array} \quad (3)$$

$$3D: \quad \frac{2}{r} \cdot \frac{dp}{dr} + \frac{d^2 p}{dr^2} = 0,$$

distinguished between radial flow (2D) and spherical flow (3D)

Isotropic permeability

For isotropic porous media the flow and the pressure distribution are similar in each radial direction. The differential equation (Eqn. 3) is generally solved for isotropic permeability by

$$2D: \quad p(r) = a \cdot \ln(r) + b \quad (4)$$

$$3D: \quad p(r) = \frac{a}{r} + b$$

Regarding the boundary conditions at the injection gate $p(r_0) = p_0$ and at the flow front $p(r_f) = 0$ leads to the pressure distribution within the fluid

$$2D: \quad p(r) = p_0 \frac{\ln\left(\frac{r}{r_f}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{r_0}{r_f}\right)} \quad \begin{array}{l} p_0 : \text{injection pressure} \\ r_0 : \text{radius of the injection gate} \\ r_f : \text{flow front radius} \end{array} \quad (5)$$

$$3D: \quad p(r) = p_0 \left(1 + \frac{r_f}{r_f - r_0} \left[\frac{r_0}{r} - 1 \right] \right)$$

The transformation of this Equation 5 allows to calculate the flow front position based on the pressure at a given point, for example the pressure measured by a sensor.

$$2D: \quad r_f(p_s) = r_0 \left(\frac{r_0}{r_s} \right)^{\left(\frac{p_0}{p_s - p_0} \right)} \quad \begin{array}{l} p_s : \text{sensor pressure} \\ r_s : \text{sensor distance from gate} \end{array} \quad (6)$$

$$3D: \quad r_f(p_s) = r_0 r_s \frac{p_s - p_0}{p_s r_s - p_0 r_0}$$

Inserting the pressure distribution (Eqn. 5) in Darcy's Law (Eqn. 1) leads to the flow velocity. During the experiment the only velocity that can be observed is the velocity of the flow front. So it is necessary to calculate the flow front as a function of time. By inserting the flow front position r_f one obtains the flow front velocity:

$$2D: \quad \frac{dr_f}{dt} = v_f(r_f) = \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{1}{\ln\left(\frac{r_f}{r_0}\right) \cdot r_f} \quad (7)$$

$$3D: \quad \frac{dr_f}{dt} = v_f(r_f) = \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot p_0 \cdot \frac{r_0}{(r_f - r_0) \cdot r_f}$$

To obtain the flow front position it is necessary to integrate Eqn. 7. This can be achieved by separating the variables and subsequently integrate over time respectively the flow front position r_f . The integration can be considered as a “modified flow front position” RF^*

$$2D: \quad RF^* := \int_{\hat{r}_f=r_0}^{r_f} \ln\left(\frac{\hat{r}_f}{r_0}\right) \cdot \frac{r_f}{r_0} \cdot d\left(\frac{r_f}{r_0}\right) = \int_{\hat{t}=0}^t \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \frac{1}{r_0^2} \cdot p_0(\hat{t}) \cdot d\hat{t} \quad (8)$$

$$3D: \quad RF^* := \int_{\hat{r}_f=r_0}^{r_f} \left[\left(\frac{\hat{r}_f}{r_0}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\hat{r}_f}{r_0}\right) \right] \cdot d\left(\frac{\hat{r}_f}{r_0}\right) = \int_{\hat{t}=0}^t \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \frac{1}{r_0^2} \cdot p_0(\hat{t}) \cdot d\hat{t}$$

In a pressure driven application it is recommendable to rise the injection pressure linearly with time to avoid fibre washing. After the time t_{ramp} the final injection pressure P_0 is reached and the injection pressure is constant:

$$p(t) = \begin{cases} 0 \leq t \leq t_{ramp} : & p(t) = \frac{t}{t_{ramp}} \cdot P_0 \\ t_{ramp} \leq t : & p(t) = P_0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The right hand side of equation 8 is integrated as

$$RF^*(t) = \begin{cases} 0 \leq t \leq t_{ramp} : & \frac{1}{2} \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \frac{1}{r_0^2} \cdot \frac{t^2}{t_{ramp}} \cdot P_0 \\ t_{ramp} \leq t : & \frac{K}{\eta \cdot \Phi} \cdot \frac{1}{r_0^2} \cdot (t - t_{ramp}) \cdot P_0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

And the left hand side results in

$$2D: \quad RF^* = \frac{1}{4} [2\rho^2 \cdot \ln(\rho) - \rho^2 + 1]; \quad \rho = \frac{r_f}{r_0} \quad (11)$$

$$3D: \quad RF^* = \frac{1}{6} [2\rho^3 - \rho^2 + 1]$$

Equation 11 can be solved in order to obtain r_f explicitly:

$$2D: \quad r_f = r_0 \cdot e^{\frac{1}{2} \left(\text{LambertW}\left(\frac{-1+4RF^*}{e}\right) + 1 \right)} \quad (12)$$

$$3D: \quad r_f = \frac{1}{2} r_0 \cdot \left(\Pi + \frac{1}{\Pi} + 1 \right); \quad \Pi = \sqrt[3]{-1 + 12RF^* + 2\sqrt{36RF^{*2} - 6RF^*}}$$

Orthotropic permeability

Flow in preforms orthotropic permeability show ellipsoidal flow front propagation. In contrast to the isotropic case where one (skalar) value K can describe the permeability of a preform, in the orthotropic case it is necessary to specify the values of three principal permeabilities and their directions. This is illustrated for the 2D case in figure 1.

The flow in the ideal test cavity within a homogeneous preform is purely radial respectively spherical. For that reason the flow velocity depends on the pressure gradient and the permeability in flow direction. A pure radial flow would require an elliptical injection gate, whereas the geometry of the gate depends on the principal values of the permeability tensor. For obvious reasons experiments are conducted with circular injection gates. Finite Element calculations show, that effect of the inlet shape vanishes very fast and are negligible [3]. Even so it is not shaped elliptical but circular in the experiment, the calculation of the flow assumes an elliptical injection port. In the equations that describe the flow model the radius of the injection gate is replaced by the direction dependent radius:

$$r_0(\alpha) = \frac{\bar{r}_0}{\sqrt{\sqrt{\frac{K_1}{K_2}} \sin^2(\alpha - \varphi) + \sqrt{\frac{K_2}{K_1}} \cos^2(\alpha - \varphi)}} \quad \begin{array}{l} K_1, K_2 : \text{main permeabilities} \\ \varphi : \text{dir. of major permeability} \end{array} \quad (13)$$

The effective permeability in a direction α is formulated by Bear in [4] and can be used to calculate the flow velocity in the direction α

$$K_{eff}(\alpha) = \frac{K_1 K_2}{K_1 \cdot \sin(\alpha - \varphi) + K_2 \cdot \cos(\alpha - \varphi)} \quad (14)$$

For the orthotropic flow model, the permeability K in the isotropic model is replaced by this direction dependent permeability K_{eff} .

For 3D measurement a general simplification that is done here is the assumption that one principal axe of the permeability tensor is always in the out of plane direction of the testing cavity. This is an acceptable restraint as most fabric preforms satisfy this requirement. Anyhow, there are preforms i.e. knitted preforms that have an anisotropic permeability tensor whose principal direction K_3 differs with the thickness direction of the mould.

SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION

The evaluation software is capable to calculate the flow front position and the pressure at each point and at each time, based on a given set of parameters $x = [K_1, K_2, \varphi, r_0]$. In a numerical optimization the parameters K_1 , K_2 , and φ , allow to minimize the absolute or the relative errors between measured values and calculated values. The parameters x_{opt} that minimize this error are taken as the preform permeabilities.

If the optimization variable is the sensor pressure p , and the optimization mode is set to minimize the absolute errors, the solution parameters x of the optimization problem

$$\sum_{k=1}^m |p(x)|^2 \rightarrow \min \quad (15)$$

can be determined by the Gauss-Newton-Iteration as follows:

$$|p(x_i) + p'(x_i)\Delta x_i| \rightarrow \min; \quad x_{i+1} \leftarrow x_i + \Delta x_i \quad (16)$$

This optimisation is implemented in Labview and can be run online while the measurement is in progress. As basis for this computation a user-defined number of measured datapoints can be used. The principle of the realized optimization is visualized for pressures in the following figure 2:

Fig. 2: Parameter optimization

A subset of the whole set of measured pressure data can be selected which contains the pressure values measured in the time interval $t_1 \leq t \leq t_2$. These values form the database for the calculation. In the beginning a set of appropriate parameters is assumed (i.e. $K_1 = 4 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$, $K_2 = 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$, $\phi = 0$, $r_0 = 0.004 \text{ m}$). Using these parameters for each point of time and for each sensor a pressure is calculated and compared with the measured pressure. This calculation is split up into the three substeps RF^* , r_f and p_s (Eqn. 10, 12 and 5). Then a linear least square optimization (Gauss-Newton) is used in order to find parameters that minimize the difference between measured and calculated pressures. Because of the non-linearity of the optimization problem several iterations are necessary. An abort condition is implemented that compares the proposed change of the parameter with its previous value. If the proposed change of each parameter is sufficiently small, the optimization is terminated and the current parameters are taken as the true permeabilities of the preform. To get a stable iteration it is necessary to scale the the parameter set Δx_i proposed by the optimization by the stepwidth λ before adding them to the current parameter set x_i .

For the described least square optimization the pressure at the sensor positions and its derivatives $\frac{\partial p}{\partial K1}, \frac{\partial p}{\partial K2}, \frac{\partial p}{\partial \phi}, \frac{\partial p}{\partial r_0}$ are required. These have been calculated using the formula manipulation software maple. The expressions become unwieldy, so the calculation of the pressure and its derivatives is separated in the three substeps RF^* , r_f and p_0 .

The size of the injection gate has a strong influence on the calculated pressures. Because of the non elliptical shape and the only approximately known radius of the injection gate it is recommendable to include the radius of the injection gate in the determination of the permeabilities.

The optimization is implemented for sensors that detect the flow front in the same manner. However, the optimization target of the least square optimization is to reduce the difference between the calculated and the measured flow front position r_f .

Fig. 3: Screenshot of evaluation software

REALISATION OF THE MEASUREMENT CELL

There are several kinds of sensors to detect the flow front position [5]. Most of the commonly used sensors allow to detect the flow front arrival. We decided to use pressure sensors which deliver continuous information still after the flow front has passed the sensor. After the flow front has passed the sensor, the data values of the pressure sensor start to raise, thus continuously providing meaningful data for permeability calculation..

Even though the cell is usually operated with a model fluid like silicon oil or glycerin, it is designed to be used with resin. This means that only components are used that can be cleaned from resin and have no cavities on their surface. For instance only pressure sensors should be used that have a flush front membrane.

Fig. 4: closed measurement cell with glass lid

The cavity height can be adapted to the recommendations of the specific application using appropriate ledges. On the one hand little cavity heights (like i.e. 2 mm) require only little amount of preforms. This means lower material costs and less effort to cut and place the preforms properly. On the other hand this allows only few discrete fibre volume contents (FVC), since only very few perform layers are needed to obtain FVC of 40 to 60 %. Another problem is the deflection of the cell during the injection. The smaller the cavity height, the higher is the relative change in FVC caused by that deflection. So for each measurement the optimal cavity height has to be chosen.

The positions of the sensors are variable and unused connectors must be closed using blind plugs (fig. 5). Particularly for the estimation of the radius of the injection gate, it is necessary to arrange the sensors both near and far from the injection gate. Because of the symmetry of the flow ellipse the sensors are steady spread over an angle range of 180° only.

Fig. 5: lower part of the test cavity with pressure sensors, injection gate and blind plugs

CELL TESTING

Some experiments were carried out to test the measurement cell. In figure 6 the pressure history of 6 sensors is shown for one injection.

Fig. 6: Measured sensor pressures at an injection pressure of $2 \cdot 10^5$ Pa

About 90 s after the injection had started the first remote sensor is reached. From that time on meaningful results can be expected, but the quality of the evaluation will increase the more sensors are reached by the fluid. The evaluation shows quite stable permeability values for the principal permeabilities K_1 and K_2 . (fig. 7). The direction of the principal axes can be determined even better. The results show principal permeabilities of about $K_1 = 8 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$ and $K_2 = 3 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$. The direction of the principal axes is stable at $\varphi = 42^\circ$:

Fig. 7: Evaluation of trial with 44 % fiber volume content, cavity height 5 mm

CONCLUSIONS

The model proposed in this work is implemented in a software (LabView), that makes evaluation of permeability measurements considerably easier and faster. By avoiding visual observation it is possible to design a very stiff cell. This is one condition to guaranty homogeneous permeability within the cell. The proposed method is able to provide reliable permeability values based on information coming from various kinds of sensors. The measurement cell presented in this paper is equipped with pressure sensors.

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